

Preferences and Challenges in Accessing Extra-Curricular Activities Opportunities in Bangladesh: Insights from a Survey

Hassan Jubair

Kushtia Government College

hassanjubair2005@gmail.com

17 May 2023

Preferences and Challenges in Accessing Extra-Curricular Activities Opportunities in Bangladesh: Insights from a Survey

Introduction:

Extra-curricular activities (ECAs) provide invaluable opportunities for personal growth and skill development. Discover the untold stories of Bangladesh's youth and their quest for Extra-Curricular Activities (ECAs). This article unveils the challenges and desires faced by these passionate individuals as they navigate the realm of ECAs. This article presents the findings of a survey conducted to explore the challenges faced by Bangladeshis in accessing ECA opportunities, their preferences for online or offline engagement, the presence of facilitative platforms, and gender-specific difficulties experienced by females in this regard.

**“In dreams of growth, they seek to soar,
Through ECAs, their spirits roar.
Challenges faced, desires ablaze,
Bangladesh's youth, embracing their maze.”**

Survey Results:

The survey aimed to gauge the perceived difficulty in finding ECA opportunities among Bangladeshis. The majority (53.3%) considered it moderately challenging, with only 6.7% finding it very easy, and 22.2% rating it as very hard.

When it comes to preferences for online or offline ECA opportunities, a significant majority (73.3%) expressed a preference for online engagements. The convenience and accessibility provided by online platforms appealed to the participants, while 26.7% still favored offline engagements for the in-person interaction and hands-on experiences they offer.

Regarding the existence of platforms facilitating ECA opportunity discovery in Bangladesh, responses varied. While 17.8% of participants acknowledged the presence of such platforms, a higher proportion (28.9%) believed there were none. The majority (53.3%) were uncertain about the existence of accessible platforms.

Motivations for participating in ECAs were explored, revealing multiple reasons. Many participants (71.1%) expressed their desire to broaden their knowledge and gain new experiences, recognizing the value of ECAs in personal growth. Additionally, 62.2% viewed ECAs as a means to enhance their prospects of studying abroad. Furthermore, 53.3% sought ECAs to improve their university applications, while 20% expressed engaging out of pure passion.

The survey also assessed the difficulty for individuals outside Dhaka in finding ECA opportunities. The results indicated that 34.4% found it very hard, highlighting the challenges faced by those residing outside the capital city. Similarly, when considering participation in national Olympiads, workshops, and offline opportunities, 37% rated it as very hard, indicating limited accessibility for those residing outside Dhaka.

A gender-specific question was included for female respondents, focusing on the additional difficulties and stigma they may face while engaging in ECAs. The findings demonstrated that a majority of female respondents perceived specific challenges. Security issues (72%), problems finding safe accommodations (60%), and a lack of family support (56%) were among the difficulties cited. Additionally, social harassment (24%) and challenges finding safe transportation options (44%) were identified as obstacles for females participating in ECAs.

Conclusion:

The survey results shed light on the challenges and preferences associated with accessing ECA opportunities in Bangladesh. The findings highlight the need for improved accessibility, support systems, and safety measures to ensure equal participation in ECAs. The strong preference for online ECAs suggests the importance of leveraging digital platforms to overcome geographic limitations. The findings also underscore the additional difficulties faced by females, emphasizing the need for targeted measures to address security concerns, social harassment, and other gender-specific obstacles.

Policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders should collaborate to establish inclusive platforms, raise awareness, and provide necessary support systems. By promoting equal access to ECAs, Bangladesh can unlock the full potential of its students, fostering personal growth, academic success, and societal contributions.

Key Takeaways:

- Strong preference for online ECA opportunities indicates the convenience and the accessibility offered by digital platforms.
- Moderate difficulty in finding ECA opportunities in Bangladesh highlights the need for improved accessibility.
- Lack of awareness about platforms facilitating opportunity discovery calls for better promotion and awareness campaigns.
- Motivations for engaging in ECAs include knowledge expansion, enhancing university applications, and studying abroad.
- Challenges faced by individuals outside Dhaka emphasize the need for improved access in regions beyond the capital city.
- Additional difficulties faced by females include security issues, lack of family support, social harassment, and accommodation and transportation concerns.
- Improved support systems, inclusive platforms, and collaboration among stakeholders are essential for addressing challenges and ensuring equal opportunities.
- Policymakers and educational institutions must work together to enhance access and inclusivity in ECA opportunities in Bangladesh.